

Studies on 1,3-Diaryl Pyrazolones and Their Derivatives

P. N. DHAL, T. E. ACHARY AND A. NAYAK

Department of Chemistry, Sambalpur University, Jyoti Vihar, Burla
and

Department of Chemistry, G. M. College, Sambalpur

Manuscript received 5 April 1974; accepted 26 July 1975

Condensation of benzoyl acetic ester and *p*-nitro benzoyl acetic ester with phenyl hydrazine furnished 1, 3-diphenyl pyrazolone and 1-phenyl 3-*p*-nitro phenyl pyrazolone respectively. These pyrazolones have been used to synthesise several merocyanines and arylidene derivatives under different conditions and the latter have been brominated to dibromo compounds. Also orange coloured azo dyes have been prepared from them after coupling them with diazotised sulphamamide. One of these dyes inhibits the growth of *T. Mentagrophytes* in a concentration of 25 µg/ml.

PHARMACOLOGICAL studies by Benigni¹ on phenyl methyl isopyrazolone shows respiratory and cardio-vascular activities. Therapeutical importance of pyrazolone and its several derivatives as bactericides and fungicides²⁻³ have been studied by several investigators. Rout *et al.*⁴ have also reported the condensation of aromatic aldehydes with 1-phenyl 3-methyl pyrazolone under different conditions which shows pyrazolone exists in tautomeric form. The present investigation describes the synthesis of 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolone and 1-phenyl 3-*p*-nitrophenyl pyrazolone from benzoyl acetic ester and *p*-nitro benzoyl acetic ester with phenyl hydrazine. 1, 3-Diphenyl pyrazolone has been used to synthesise various carbocyanines ($n = 0$ and 1) by condensing it with (i) methyl mercapto quaternary salts ($n = 0$) and with (ii) its acetanilido methylene intermediate with various 2-methyl quaternary salts ($n = 1$) using alcohol in the presence of triethylamine. Absorption maxima of the dyes shows a vinylenic shift of approximately 80-100 mµ; when n is increased from 0 to 1. The structures of the carbocyanines have also been confirmed from NMR studies. In case of the dyes ($n = 1$), the methin protons appear at 7.0-7.6δ in the form of two unsymmetrical doublets. The J values, which are in the order of 12-16 cps indicate that the methin protons are in trans configuration.

Both the pyrazolones have been condensed with different aromatic aldehydes in two different conditions using different solvents and some generalisations have been made as regards the mechanisms of condensation are concerned. When acetic acid is used it afforded mono-arylidene derivatives (II) along with bis-pyrazolone compounds (III), which were isolated by diluting the solution after separation of the former. However, the formation of mono-arylidene derivatives in case of *p*-dimethylamino benzaldehyde and salicylaldehyde and bis-pyrazolone compounds in case of benzaldehyde and anisaldehyde were not observed. The formation of the products

can be explained by additive elimination mechanism, which can be represented as follows :

Compound II add up with bromine water and are highly coloured and compound III give no colouration with ferric chloride and most of them are colourless. The arylidene compounds were isolated in 50-60% yield whereas the bis-pyrazolone compounds in keto form were isolated in 30-40% yield. But when the reaction was carried out using alcohol and piperidine bis-pyrazolones (IV) were obtained. These compounds gave violet colouration with ferric chloride. The possible mechanism for the formation of these compounds may be as follows. (see next page)

The above mechanism is supported by the fact that when 1:1 molar proportion of aldehyde and pyrazolone were used almost half of aldehyde left unreacted, which were separated as bisulphite compounds from the solution. But when the proportion was changed to 1:2, there were negligible amount of unreacted components. The IR spectrum of benzylidene bis-1,3-diphenyl pyrazolone (IV; $\phi = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) shows no C = O absorption but a broad peak at 3520 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of enolic structure. The

mono-benzylidene derivative (II) were brominated to dibromo compounds using bromine in acetic acid. The pyrazolone also gave orange coloured azodyes when coupled with diazotised sulphanilamide.

Pharmacological tests: A few of the arylidene derivatives, their dibromo compounds and the azo dyes prepared from pyrazolones were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities against different micro organisms. The diazo compound derived from 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolone inhibits the growth of *S. aureus* and *T. Mentagrophytes* in a minimum inhibitory concentration of 25 μ g/ml.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. I.R. spectra of the compounds were taken in hexachloro butadiene in Perkin Elmer 257 grating spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were recorded on Varian 100Hz spectrophotometer in CDCl_3 using TMS as internal standard. The chemical shifts are expressed in δ (pp.m) downfield from TMS.

1,3-Diphenyl pyrazolone :

A mixture of benzoyl acetic ester (5.2 ml) and phenyl hydrazine (4.2 ml) was heated on a water bath for two hours. After cooling the mixture was agitated with ether and the solid separated was crystallised from alcohol. Yield — 6.5 gm., M.P. 137° (Found : C; 75.93, H; 4.72, N; 11.23. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires C; 76.27, H; 5.00, N; 11.76). $\nu(\text{cm}^{-1})$; 1600 (C=O), 1150 (—CO—CH₂—), 1520, 1560 (C=N). δ ; 6.0 (2H, s), 7.3 and 7.8 (m, corresponding to —C—C₆H₅ and N—C₆H₅ respectively).

1-Phenyl 3-p-nitrophenyl pyrazolone :

It was isolated in 65% yield as yellow needles from p-nitro benzoyl acetic ester and phenyl hydrazine as above. M.P. 186°.

4-(3-Methyl 4-phenyl thiazolin-2-ylidene)-1, 3-di-phenyl pyrazolone:

It was prepared from 2-methyl mercapto 4-phenyl thiazole methiodide (0.3g) and diphenyl pyrazolone (0.24 g) using alcohol and triethylamine. Yield 60%, M.P. 173°. (Found : C; 73.12; H; 4.56, N;

10.15. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{SO}$ requires C; 73.34, H; 4.64, N; 10.26), λ_{max} in alcohol 410 μ .

4-(3-Methyl benzothiazolin-2-ylidene) 1,3-diphenylpyrazolone

It was prepared from 2-methyl mercapto benzothiazole methiodide in 65% yield as pale yellow needles. M.P. 176°, λ_{max} in ethanol 425 μ .

4-(Acetanilido methylene) 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolone :

1,3-Diphenyl pyrazolone (2.4 g) and diphenyl formamide (2g) in acetic anhydride (20 ml) were refluxed for 30 minutes and cooled. The solid obtained was filtered and washed with alcohol. Yield — 3.2 gm, M.P. 182°.

4-(3-Methyl 4-phenyl thiazolin 2-ylidene-ethylidene) 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolone :

The above acetanilido methylene intermediate (0.35g) and 2-methyl 4-phenyl thiazole methiodide (0.32 g) in ethanol were heated under reflux with triethylamine (2 drops) for about 20 min. The solution was cooled and diluted with water. The solid separated was crystallised from alcohol as orange needles. M.P. 187° (Found : C; 74.36, H; 4.57, N; 9.28. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{SO}$ requires C; 74.48, H; 4.83, N; 9.65), λ_{max} in alcohol 515 μ ; log ϵ ; 4.1362. δ ; 7.25 and 7.55 (2.H.d), 3.72 (s, >NCH₃), 8.15 (m, aromatic protons).

4-(1-Methylquinoline-2-ylidene ethylidene) 1, 3-di-phenyl pyrazolone :

It was isolated as dark shining needles in 50% yield. M.P. 131°, λ_{max} in alcohol. 540 μ ., log ϵ ; 4.6281 (Found : C; 80.16, H; 5.17, N; 10.25. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{O}$ requires C; 80.39, H; 5.21, N; 10.42). δ ; 6.8 and 7.15 (2H, d), 3.9 (s, >NCH₃) and centered at 8.15 (16-proton multiplet).

4-(4-Methylquinoline-2-ylidene ethylidene) 1, 3-di-phenyl pyrazolone :

It was isolated as dark coloured needles from lepidine methiodide in 50% yield. M.P. 187°. (Found : C; 79.82, H; 5.39, N; 10.33. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{O}$ requires C; 80.39, H; 5.21, N; 10.42), λ_{max} in ethanol 600 μ , log ϵ ; 4.8357. δ ; 6.8 and 7.1 (2H, d), 4.05 (s, >N—CH₃) and centered at 8.15 (16-proton multiplet).

4-(3-Methylbenzo-thiazolin-2-ylidene ethylidene) 1, 3-diphenyl pyrazolone :

It was obtained in 75% yield as shining orange needles. M.P. 184°, λ_{max} 504 μ in alcohol, log ϵ ; 4.6819.

General procedure for the condensation of aldehydes with pyrazolone in acetic acid :

1,3-Diphenyl pyrazolone (2.4 g) was dissolved in acetic acid (20 ml) and the solution was treated with aldehyde (1 molar proportion) and kept in the room temperature. After a period of half an hour to 2 hrs the solids separated in most of the cases. But with

p-dimethylamino benzaldehyde and salicylaldehyde no solids separated even after a week. The solids were filtered and washed with acetic acid. These compounds correspond to the structure II (monobenzylidene derivatives). The filtrates, when diluted with water gave almost colourless solids in quantitative yield excepting in case of benzaldehyde and anisaldehyde. The solids were filtered and crystallised from alcohol.

4-Benzylidene 1, 3-diphenyl pyrazolone : (II; $\phi = C_6H_5$)

It was isolated as shining yellow needles. Yield — 3.2g. M.P. 223° (Found : C; 81.52, H; 4.36, N; 8.63. $C_{22}H_{15}N_2O$ requires C; 81.73, H; 4.64, N; 8.94). ν (cm^{-1}); 1520 and 1560 (C = N), 1630 (C = O); δ ; 6.2 (s, 1H) and multiplet centered at 8.1 corresponding to 15 atomic protons.

Benzylidene bis-pyrazolone in keto form from *p*-chloro benzaldehyde :

After separating the mono benzylidene derivative the filtrate was diluted with sufficient amount of water and kept overnight. The pale yellow precipitate separated, and was crystallised from alcohol. Yield — 1.2 g. M.P. 136° (Found : C; 74.72, H; 4.16, N; 9.25. $C_{37}H_{27}N_4O_2Cl$ requires C; 75.00, H; 4.66, N; 9.42).

Benzylidene bis-pyrazolone in enol form from benzaldehyde :

An alcoholic solution of 1, 3-diphenyl pyrazolone (4.8 g) and benzaldehyde (1.2 ml) was treated with

4 drops of piperidine and kept at room temperature for one hour to 2 days with different aldehydes. The crystalline solid separated was washed with alcohol. Yield — 5.3g. M.P. 236°. (Found : C; 77.25, H; 4.56, N; 9.62. $C_{37}H_{28}N_4O_2$ requires C; 77.50, H; 5.00, N; 10.00), ν (cm^{-1})3500 (broad peak due to OH).

4-Bromo (4- α -bromo benzyl)-1, 3-diphenyl pyrazolone :

The mono-benzylidene compound obtained from benzaldehyde was brominated with bromine in acetic acid according to our previous procedure⁵. The analytical data etc. of different types of compounds have been listed in Tables 1 and 2.

4-(*p*-Sulphonamido phenyl) 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolone :

Sulphanilamide (0.5g) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (1 ml) and water (15 ml) was diazotised with $NaNO_2$ (0.25 g) in 30 ml of water) in an ice bath. The resulting diazo solution was gradually added with stirring to a previously cooled solution of pyrazolone (0.24 g) in $NaOH$ (0.5 g in 20 ml of water). The solution was further stirred for one hour during which an orange coloured azo dye separated which was crystallised from alcohol. Yield — 0.3 g M.P. 192°. (Found : N; 16.33. $C_{21}H_{17}N_5SO_3$ requires N; 16.65%).

4-(*p*-Sulphonamido phenyl 1-phenyl 3-*p*-nitro phenyl pyrazolone :

It was obtained as orange powder in 40% yield from 1-phenyl 3-*p*-nitro phenyl pyrazolone and diazotised sulphanilamide as above. M.P. 210°.

TABLE I

ϕ	Mono-arylidene derivatives (II)			Dibromo compounds		
	M.P. °C	% Nitrogen		M.P. °C	% Bromine	
		Found	Calcd.		Found	Calcd.
1, 3-Diphenyl pyrazolone						
C_6H_5	—	—	—	155	32.84	33.06
<i>p</i> - $CH_3O \cdot C_6H_4$ -	172	7.75	7.90	85	31.01	31.12
<i>p</i> -Cl. C_6H_4 -	208	7.32	7.79	120	—	—
<i>p</i> -Br. C_6H_4 -	222	6.86	6.96	98	42.15	42.63
<i>p</i> - $NO_2 \cdot C_6H_4$ -	174(d)	10.35	10.58	83	—	—
1-Phenyl 3- <i>p</i> -nitro phenyl pyrazolone						
C_6H_5	243	11.11	11.38	206	30.65	30.24
<i>p</i> - $CH_3O \cdot C_6H_4$ -	184	10.25	10.52	212	28.32	28.62
<i>p</i> -Cl. C_6H_4 -	225	10.22	10.40	210	—	—
<i>p</i> - $NO_2 \cdot C_6H_4$ -	258	13.75	13.52	183	27.63	27.87

TABLE 2

ϕ	Bis-pyrazolone compound keto form (III)			Bis-pyrazolone compound enol form (IV)		
	M.P. °C	% Nitrogen		M.P. °C	% Nitrogen	
		Found	Calcd.		Found	Calcd.
1, 3-Diphenyl pyrazolone						
C ₆ H ₅ -	—	—	—	236	9.86	10.00
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	—	—	—	216	9.32	9.42
<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -	136	9.23	9.41	232	9.30	9.41
<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄ -	160	8.65	8.75	—	—	—
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ -	108	11.45	11.58	221	11.31	11.58
<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ -	—	—	—	214	—	—
<i>o</i> -HO.C ₆ H ₄ -	—	—	—	205	—	—
1-Phenyl 3- <i>p</i> -nitro phenyl pyrazolone						
C ₆ H ₅ -	224	12.51	12.92	257	12.80	12.92
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	205	12.04	12.35	230	12.01	12.35
<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -	205	11.97	12.27	242	12.61	12.27
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ -	195	14.32	14.10	255	14.42	14.10
<i>o</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -	214	12.43	12.27	249	12.11	12.27
<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ -	—	—	—	215	13.96	14.14
<i>o</i> -HO.C ₆ H ₄ -	181	12.29	12.61	234	12.36	12.61

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. A. R. Katritzky, University of East Anglia, U.K. for his kind suggestions in interpreting NMR spectra, to Dr. V. C. Vora of Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow for the biological screening of the compounds. A financial assistance from U.G.C., New Delhi to one of the authors (A.N.) is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. R. BENIGNI, *Minerva. Med.* 1941, **1**, 436.
2. G. B. CRIPPA and S. MAFFEI, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1942, **72**, 97.
3. CHATTERJEE and GHOSH, *Proc. Asiatic Soc.*, Bengal, 1919, 15.
4. S. NANDA, D. PATI, A. S. MITRA and M. K. ROUT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **10**, 833.
5. P. N. DHAL, T. E. ACHARYA, A. NAYAK and M. K. ROUT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **10**, 680.